

Perceived Social Support Depression and Pain in Arthritis Patient

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Abstract

In current study the effect of perceived social support on pain intensity and level of depression in arthritis patients was investigated. The aim was to test the stress-buffering hypothesis which suggests that an adequate level of social support if provided in time will decrease harmful consequences of stressors on health. It was assumed that high level of perceived social support will decrease intensity of pain and level of depression in arthritis patients. The sample consisted of (N=60) female arthritis outpatients selected from three hospitals of Peshawar, namely, Lady reading, Hayatabad Medical Complex, and Khyber Teaching through Convenient Sampling Technique. The Multi-Dimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (Zimet et al., 1988) was administered to measure social support available, the Visual Analogue Scale (Gracely, McGrath & Dubner, 1978) was used to measure intensity of pain and the Siddiqui Shah Depression Scale (Siddiqui, & Shah, 1997) was administered to measure the level of depression of the participants. Results showed that participants who reported higher social support available experienced low intensity of pain and low level of depression than those reported low social support available. The results support hypotheses. The findings have important implications in clinical settings, for the medical doctors, and nurses to recognize this psychological factor and to encourage family members, friends and significant others to provide social support to the patients, so that they can cope with their disease effectively.

Introduction

Arthritis is an autoimmune disorder having certain symptoms such as swelling of joints, change in cartilage, destruction of bone, pain, and later systemic inflammation (McInnes, & Schett (2011). The exact rate of the arthritis cannot be determined because of a wide variety of symptoms for which patients seek medical help. Globally prevalence of arthritis has been reported at around 1%. Some countries reveal reduce in prevalence (Gibofsky, 2012). Overall the disorder is more common in women and has been reported to increase with age, with highest rates revealed in women older than 65 years (Scott, & Wolfe, 2010). Further, patients having arthritis have higher morbidity, disability and poor quality of life (Kiltz, & Heijde (2009). The exact cause is still not known, however, risk factors due to genetics is about 50% (Scott, & Wolfe, 2010).

A lot of research suggests that arthritis is associated with depression. Research that used interviews and psychiatric assessment found the rate of depression in arthritis patients about 13 to 20 %. The prevalence depends on certain socio-demographic and disease related characteristics of population such as chronicity, severity and female gender (Creed, 1990). Thus, arthritis patients compared to general population are more likely to suffer from depression. In arthritis depression not only leads to the additional burden such as increase in intensity of pain but at the same time also interact with how patients perceive their disease, cope with their physical disorder, communicate with general practitioner and with rheumatologist (Murphy, Dickens, Creed & Bernstein, 2017).

In arthritis patients' depression has also been found to increased level of pain and this relation has been found significant even after controlling certain diseases related factors (Dickens, McGowan, Clark-cater, & Creed, 2001). There are many arguments among researchers regarding this issue whether depression contributes to intensity of pain or whether pain is simply a reaction to depression (Romano, & Turner, 1995). Majority of research in this field are cross-sectional in nature, from which casual inferences cannot be drawn. Longitudinal studies, on the other hand, are few in this area and found no causal relationship between depression and pain (Wolfe, & Hawley, 1993, Magni, Moreschi, Luchini, & Merskey, 1994). Research in other patients with chronic musculoskeletal pain, however, show that association between depression and pain acts in bi-directions, with pain intensifies depression and depression in turn increases pain (Romano & Turner, 1995). Further depression has also been shown to increase functional disability in arthritis patients, which in turn, predicts more disability days, and more hospitalization. Thus, pain and disability are critical stressors that are more likely to increase depression in arthritic patients. However, most of the patients who experience intense pain and

disability but do not develop depression, suggests the involvement of other factors as well (Adham, Creed, Bagshaw, James, & Swannell, 2019).

Social factors in conceptual model of pain are the most important (Bogossian, 2007). As a complex concept social support refers to resources provided and to promote welfare of the receiver, while in situations when a person needs support and he/she feels that it is available then it is referred to as perceived social support (López-Martínez, Esteve-Zarazaga, & Ramírez-Maestre 2008). Among social factors such as lack of social support and social stresses such as financial problems have been found to be strongly associated with depression in arthritic patients (Cramer, Henderson, Scott, 1997). Numerous researches have demonstrated that social support reduces depression level and pain intensity in arthritis patients. For example, Brandstetter, et al, (2016) in their study examined depression, intensity of pain and social support in 361 arthritis patients. Findings of linear regression analyses demonstrated that social support and pain both were significantly associated with depression. Low social support and high intensity of pain predicted depression in patients.

An important question in this regard is whether women patients with arthritis who are married, divorced or widowed and those unmarried experience same level of depression and severity of pain. Kraaimaat, van Dam-Baqen and Bijlsma (2007) addressing this issue investigated the effect of social support, in 53 widowed and divorced arthritis patients, 22 unmarried female patients, and 127 women living with spouse. The results showed no significant difference between unmarried and those living with their spouse in terms of depression and anxiety, however, widowed and divorced who reported less social support available experienced more depression and anxiety and higher intensity of pain. Revenson, Schiaffino, Majeroviz and Gibofsky (1991) in 101 recently diagnosed arthritis patients examined social support and symptoms of depression. Results revealed that helpful and positive support received from family and close friends was related to low level of depression, while problematic relationship with family and low support was associated with higher depression in these patients.

In his longitudinal study of consecutive four annual assessments Benka et al., (2011) investigated functional disability, pain, psychological distress and joint tenderness in arthritis patients. The major goal was to find an association between psychological distress and social support. Findings demonstrated that those arthritis patients who experienced higher emotional support reported lower pain and psychological distress after controlling other relevant variables. In another study researchers examined the effect of social support on coping with pain, disappointment in support and satisfaction with support in 73 adult arthritis patients. Findings showed positive association between satisfaction with social support and adaptive coping strategies and between dissatisfaction and use of maladaptive coping. Results conclude that social support plays an important role in fighting and promoting adaptive coping strategies (Holtzman, Newth, & Delongis, 2004). Similar results were obtained by other research (Ferreira & Sherman, 2007).

Numerous research has well documented and recognized positive effect of social support on psychological well-being of the patients suffering from various chronic disorders and in general population as well (Abraido-Lanza, 2004, Krokavcova et al., 2008, Treharne, Lyons, Booth & Kitas, 2007). As social support is a multi-dimensional phenomenon in Cohen's view (Cohen & Wills, 1985) when studying its effect it should be taken into account what kind of social support reflects demand of the situation. For making a successful adaptation to any chronic disorder such as arthritis, patients need support from different sources, among them support from close interpersonal ties is the most important (Dirik & Karanci, 2010). Keeping in view the aforementioned the present research aimed to examine effect of social support on the level of depression and severity of pain in arthritis patients.

Objectives

To investigate effect of perceived social support on the level of depression in arthritis patients.

To determine if an adequate social support available will reduce intensity of pain among arthritis patients.

Hypotheses

Arthritis patients having high perceived social support will experience low level of depression as compared to those with low perceived social support.

Participants satisfied with the available social support will experience less severe pain than those not satisfied.

High level of depression and intense pain will predict low social support in arthritis patients.

Method

Study Design

In present study Between Group Design was used to examine effect of social support on level of depression and pain intensity among arthritis patients.

Sample

The sample consisted of (N= 60) arthritis female outpatients selected from three hospitals of Peshawar, namely, Lady reading, Hayatabad Medical Complex, and Khyber Teaching through Convenient Sampling Technique. The size of sample was calculated using software Sample Size Determination in health studies (Lawanga, & Lemeshow, 1991). Demographic information of sample has been shown in table no 1. The

participants having two years of being diagnosed, were not suffering from any other serious disease, such as cardiovascular, hepatitis or diabetes and had not experienced any traumatic events in the near past were included.

Instruments

Visual Analogue Scale (VAS)

The VAS is widely used scale for measurement of pain intensity (Gracely, McGrath & Dubner, 1978). The scale comprised of a 100 millimeter horizontal line. The endpoints of the line are marked by the responses as no pain to unbearable pain. Participant responds to the VAS by placing 11 marks at the point along the scale that best describes pain intensity he/she experiences. The VAS can also be converted into graphic rating scale. The intensity of pain is measured by distance from left endpoint to the mark made by respondent which reveals measure of intensity of pain respondent in terms of quantity. The VAS has been used in numerous research to measure the outcomes of pharmacological and cognitive behavioral interventions (Parker, et al, 1988; Radlely, Young, & Anderson, 1987).

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS)

The MSPSS developed by Zimet et al., (1988) consists of three subscales, namely, Family, Friends and Significant Other and measures perception of social support available from family, friends or significant other. It is a seven point Likert scale ranging from 1 very strongly disagree to 7 very strongly agree. The reliability of the subscales and of whole scale range from 0.85 to 0.91. It was translated in Urdu by Jibeen and Khalique (2010). In current research the Urdu translated version of the MSPSS prepared by Jibeen and Khalique was used.

Siddique Shah Depression Scale (SSDS)

The SSDS was developed by Siddiqui and Shah in 1997 at the National Institute of Psychology Quaid-I-Azam University Islamabad. The scale measures level of depression in clinical and non-clinical population. It consists of 30 items, each having four possible alternatives, i-e, never, (0) sometime, (1) usually (3) and always (4). The reliability of the scale determined by split half method for the clinical group is 0.79 and for non-clinical group is 0.80. The correlation of the scale with the Zung Depression Self Rating Scale is 0.55 and with the psychiatric rating of the depression is 0.04.

Procedure

Permission from the hospital authority and verbal consent from each patient was obtained. Each participant was interviewed individually. The participants were divided into low and high social support available groups on the basis of scores they obtained on the MSPSS. Later the VAS and the SSDS were administered to measure the level of depression and pain intensity of the participants.

Results

Table 1

Reliability Analyses of Scales on Present Data

Scales	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
MSPSS	0.69	12
SSDS	0.78	30

Table 2

Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

	Low SSS(n=32)		High SSS(n=28)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Age in Years				
31-40	09	28.12%	08	28.57%
41-50	12	37.5%	09	32.14%
51-64	11	34.37%	11	39.28%
Total	32		28	
Education				
Primary	10	31.25%	07	25.00%
Middle	16	50.00%	10	35.71%

Metric	04	12.50%	11	39.28%
Illiterate	02	6.25%		
Total	32		28	
Socioeconomic Status				
Middle(40,000)	11	34.37%	08	28.57%
Lower (Rs.20,000)	21	65.62%	20	71.42%
Total	32		28	
Duration of Symptoms of Illness before				
Diagnosis	11	3.37%	09	32.14%
0-5 months	21	65.62%	19	7.85s%
5-6 months	32		28	
Total				

Note: SSS= Social Support Scorers

Table 3

Mean Difference between Low and High Social Support Scorers on Siddiqui Shah Depression Scale

Note: SSS= Social Support Scorers, LL=Lower Limits, UL=Upper Limits

Groups of Patients	N	M	SD	t-Value	P	LL	UL	Cohen's d
Low SSS	32	45.80	16.14	4.84	.00	05.88	09.45	1.06
High SSS	28	33.69	03.66					

Findings in the above table show that arthritis patients who scored low on the MSPSS obtained high scores on the SSDS than with the high scorers on the MSPSS. These results support our first hypothesis of the study.

Table 4

Mean Difference between High and Low Social Support Groups on Visual Analogue Scale

	LowSSS(n=32)		HighSSS(n=28)		t-Values	P	Cohen'sd
	M	S D	M	S D			
Overalls	15.19	4.75	8.2	4.84	4.12	0.00	1.45
Pain Intensity							
Day Time	11.90	2.17	4.61	5.39	4.13	0.00	1.77
Pain Intensity							
Night Time	11.42	2.89	3.61	4.66	4.87	0.00	2.01
Pain Intensity							

Note: SSS= Social Support Scorers

Results in table 4 reveal significant difference between two groups of arthritis patients on the VAS. Patients with low scores on the MSPSS scored higher on the three subscale of VAS as compared to patients who scored high on the MSPSS. These findings support second hypothesis of the study.

Table 5

Regression Analysis for Variables Predicting low social support

Model	β	R2	$\Delta R2$	95%CI	95%CI	
					LL	UL
1 Constant	4.12			1.23	6.82	
DEP	0.384**	0.155	0.155	0.285	0.47	
2 Constant	14.97			8.88	20.51	
DEP	0.315**		0.066	0.184	0.37	

PAI	0.310**			
		0.081	0.391	0.162

Note: β =Standardized regression, R^2 =Explained variance, ΔR^2 =Change in R^2 ,** $P < .01$, LL=Lower Limit, UL=Upper Limit, DEP=Depression, PAI=Pain Intensity

Table 5 reveals regression analysis between low perceived social support and variables i-e, depression and pain. About 15.2 % of the variance in low perceived social support accounted for depression, while depression in combination with pain explains 27.8% of the variance. This result also demonstrates that when intensity of pain will be high, perceived satisfaction with social support will be low.

Discussion

Results of present research conclude that low social support significantly influence symptoms of depression and severity of pain among arthritis patients. The results reveal that arthritis patients having low social support experience high level of depression and pain intensity than patients with higher social support. Arthritis a disease leads to numerous changes in terms of metabolic, biochemical and physiological. These changes between breakdown and repair of joint tissue simultaneously occur due to imbalance in equilibrium (Mounach, et al., 2008). The common attributing factor includes age, but numerous other co-morbid conditions can worsen disorder and intensifying pain in patients (Adams, Leddy, McNutly, O'Connor, & Guilak 2014, Jones, et al., 2015). The current research study was an effort to investigate the effect of social support on the level of depression and pain severity among arthritis patients. The results of current research are in accordance with earlier studies which demonstrate a close association between low social support and high level of depression and severe pain among arthritis patients (Brandstetter, et al, 2016, Gregory, Kenneth, Perry & Nicassio, 1989, Revenson, Schiaffino, Majeroviz & Gibofsky, 1991).

Numerous research demonstrate that arthritis patients having lack of social support report higher level of depression and more severe pain than those with high social support available. For example, Holla et al., (2018) in a five years longitudinal study examined relationship among daily stressors, depressive symptoms, social support and avoidance coping and development of arthritis. The results showed no effect of the said variables on the development of arthritis, however, those who reported low level of social support and high level of depression experienced increase in the intensity of pain, tender joint count and morning stiffness.

Almeida et al., (2019) in a study examined association between pain catastrophization and social support among 28 patients having chronic pain in knee. Catastrophization in the study refers to way patient ask for help and assistance from others which reinforces pain expression when provided especially by spouse, and lower pain severity when given by other than spouse. The results showed that patients who reported high social support given by close one experienced high levels of catastrophization which, in turn, increased in patients pain intensity and asking for social support. However in patients, who were given high social support by others not significant, reported decrease in their severity of pain. The high level of depression and catastrophization were also associated with suicidal ideation in patients having chronic musculoskeletal pain (Edward et al., 006). Similar findings were reported by other research (Linton, (2010).

Findings of present study are in line with an early study by Gregory et al., (1989). In their study these researchers examined in 233 patients of rheumatoid arthritis after controlling the functional disability, demographic, and the variable of pain effect, whether adverse effect of pain among arthritis patients can be decreased by social support or can be buffered. The results showed that patients who scored higher on the emotional sub-scale of the social support scale reported less severe pain and low level of depression than those did not perceive the emotional support. Findings concluded that emotional support contributed change in severity of pain and level of depression in these patients.

In their study Allam, Kostova, Nakamoto and Schulz (2015) among 157 arthritis patients investigated the impact of an online social support web-based intervention and playing games on website, on the utilization with health care, physical activity, knowledge of arthritis, over use of medication and empowerment in arthritis patients. Patients were classified randomly to one of the four experimental conditions each having a different access to online social support and playing games. The control group consisted of participants that had no access to website. Using the interrupted time series design, measures were done at three time points, i-e, pre-test, two months later post-test and then after another two months at a follow up. Utilization with health care, and physical activity were the primary outcomes while arthritis knowledge and empowerment were secondary outcomes, both were reported by self. Multilevel linear mixed models were run to analyze change in the outcomes. The findings revealed that participants of experimental group showed improvement in certain variables, such as their physical activity increased, utilization with health care decreased, and they experienced more empowerment than participants in the control group. Further, result revealed that participants of the experimental group were more involved in playing games than the control group in response to web-based intervention.

Tan et al., (2022) in a recent study using a cross section design investigated the relationship of pain and social support, with self-perceived burden and the kinesiophobia among elderly patients having knee

arthritis. Kinesiophobia in the study described fear of damage of a part or parts of the body as a result of exercise or physical activities which increases worry of pain. Findings revealed a negative correlation between pain, social support and self-perceived burden and kinesiophobia, and positive correlation between self-perceived burden and kinesiophobia. The above mentioned empirical evidences strongly support findings and hypotheses of the present study.

Conclusion

The findings of the research conclude that the social support is one of the most important factors that contribute to lower severity of pain and level of depression in arthritis patients.

Limitations and Suggestions

Like any research the present study is not out of limitations which future researchers need to consider while planning their research. There are certain other variables such as very low socioeconomic status, and arthritis patients having addiction with various substances, which future researchers need to focus. The present research investigated effect of perceived social support on severity of pain, and level of depression in arthritis patients, future researchers need to investigate the impact of social support on patients having other physical diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular, high blood pressure, diabetes and hepatitis. Further, future researchers need to examine role of emotional support provided by medical and paramedical staff to get more information which in turn, will maximize the effect of different pharmaceuticals and psychological intervention in patients.

Implications

The findings of the present research have important implications. To get maximum benefits from different medical treatment, at initial stage of the disease screening of the social support should be included as a part of the treatment. Patients having lack of perceived social support should be subjected to appropriate psychological intervention which should be continued till enough stability in course of treatment is obtained. Management of the different kind of social support will allow patients to feel being cared, and relax which in turn will reduce their pain and depression and will maximize benefits from their medical treatment.

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